

Historical and Ethical Perspectives on the Election of the Deacons in Acts 6:1-8: Implications for National Integration

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Abstract

After the birth of the church and the ascension of Jesus, the church membership began to increase tremendously to a point that the apostles could not solely oversee all the affairs and sectors in the church. This resulted to problem of negligence in the daily distribution of food which affected the Hellenists. This in turn led to grumbling and it threatened the unity of the church. What were the specific solution(s) proffered by the apostles to curb the occurrence of such menace? Could such solutions(s) be applicable today in Nigeria which faces similar situation? Today's Nigeria is threatened and ravaged by systemic corruption and injustice. This, therefore, has birthed agitations for breakup of the country and deepened divisions among various ethnic nationalities. Some ethnic groups such as Igbo are agitating for Biafra and some Yoruba are also demanding for an Oduduwa nation among others. The political elites appear helpless as exemplified in the government's inability to curtail the situation. Government's efforts in addressing the problem have focused more on military approach without much attention to the role of religious values and practices in solving the problem. The thrust of this paper therefore, is to examine how the early Apostles handled or solved the problem which would have marred and disintegrated the church and proffered similar solution to Nigeria's situation. The paper employed historical method as interpretative framework and recommends apostolic method of election of deacons to solving critical problems(s) in Nigeria.

Keywords: Election, Deacons, Implications, National integration

Introduction

History of the birth of the early church is not obscured. The church which is also known as *ecclesia* in Greek has its predictive origin from the Old Testament. It was referred to as the Temple of God, in this regard as a building. The word *kyriakon* is also used in reference to the Lord's house. Other appellations used include the sheep of God or flock of God. In this metaphoric wise, it refers to people of God and God being their shepherd. This predictive appellation came to fulfillment in Jesus Christ who affirmed that He was the good shepherd. Some scholars hold to Jesus' assertion to build the church upon the affirmation of Peter that Jesus is the Christ, "upon this rock I will build my church" (Matt. 16: 18) as the birth of the church, while other school of thought is of the view that the church was birthed on the day of Pentecost when the Holy Spirit descended upon the disciples at the upper room¹. An event which led to three thousand converts being added to the church. From that epoch the church began to spread and increase from place to place, city to city, etc. So, in the New Testament, church that is, *ekklesia* which connotes a local congregation of Christian and does not necessarily mean a building. As noted by Walker "...although we often speak of these congregations collectively as the NT Church or the early church, no NT writer uses *ekklesia* in this collective way. An *ekklesia* was a meeting or assembly. Its commonest use was for public assembly of citizens duly summoned, which was a feature of all the cities outside Judaea where the gospel was planted (Acts 10:19:39)."²

However, the term *ekklesia* as used in NT (Matt. 16:18) was also used in the Septuagint (LXX) among the Jews for the 'congregation' of Israel which was constituted at Sinai and from that time they assembled before the Lord for annual feast (Acts 7:38). Although, every local congregation is seen as the 'church of God' (1 Cor. 1:2), the church is also known as the Bride of Christ³, which is a "a prominent symbol and metaphor used in Scripture

to describe God's relationship with his beloved bride, the church."⁴ According to Jegede, the New Testament usage of the term church connotes gathering of believers, an organized body, "consisting of all the believers in any locality. It is the universal church."⁵ In line with this Adeniyi sees church as an organization driven by purpose of evangelizing and transforming the society.⁶ The early Christian Church began in Jerusalem and the surrounding area. It later grew out the Jewish tradition. Jesus and his disciples were all Jews. It is of note that "the first Christians, therefore, did not meet in separate churches but continued to meet in the local Jewish synagogues."⁷ After the birth of the church and the ascension of Jesus, there was a tremendous growth in the church.

Background of the Election of the Deacons

The Church in Jerusalem was where the apostles gathered after the ascension of Jesus Christ. Having been empowered through the outpouring of the Holy Spirit upon the disciples on the day of Pentecost, there was great harvest of souls. Three thousand converts were added to the church through Peter's preaching that very day (Acts 2:14-41). Evidently, it was as a result of the acts of the Holy Spirit through the apostles. This was the beginning of the growth and expansion of the church. The membership of the church began to increase nearly on daily basis as miracles, signs and wonders were performed through the apostles by God (Acts 2:43). The sick people were healed, lame walked (Acts 3:1-11), "...and the Lord added to the church daily such as should be saved" (Acts 2:47). Paul Mumo Kisau notes that "the increasing number of believers made it more difficult to distribute goods effectively, resulting in some widows being overlooked in the distribution of food."⁸ This led to grumbling and emanated complaints that Greek speaking Jews from other countries other than Israel were being neglected by Aramaic speaking Jews who were born in Israel. Both groups were Jews, so it was not an incident of racial discrimination but marginalization. They were both citizens of Israel's nation. As rightly observed by Kisau, the community of goods had not failed but the system of distribution had proved to be flawed.⁹ The national cake was still constant but its distribution was questionable, flawed, unjustifiable and rancorous.

Looking at the rate of the population of the church which was on increase nearly every day, the apostles alone could no longer cope with the members and ensure fair distribution. The eleven apostles being congested with other ministerial work were also occupied with table services at ratio 1 to 454.6 at population rate of 5,000 members in Acts 4:4 which could have increased as shown in Acts 5:1¹⁰. Could the apostles have time for their primary assignments? Would they not become fatigued? In a situation where one person fuses or few persons fuse power and responsibility to himself or themselves there are bound to be negligent in some other areas. However, in the early church, the system did work in that they soon became aware that there was a problem beckoning for urgent solution. As the situation report came to the notice of the apostles, they requested that seven men be appointed to be sure that everyone received what they needed but such ones to be appointed must meet certain qualifications which were stated by the apostles.

The Qualifications of (would-be) Deacons

Every important position or office has certain qualifications or requirements which must be met by the aspirants or would be appointees. Since the birth of the church in New Testament narratives, Acts 6:1-7 is the second place or instance where certain criteria were given before choosing a person to occupy an office or position in the church. The first instance occurred in Acts 1:12-26 where Matthias was chosen to replace Judas Iscariot; and the second instance is Acts 6:1-7. As rightly noted by Julius, "the nature of every job or work specifies the type of employees or workers to be employed. The duties to be carried out by ushers or deacons specify their qualities or qualifications and the type of person who can take up the post."¹¹ The apostles stated three major qualifications that must be looked for in the people to be elected as the deacons. Although the word or term "deacon" is not directly used in Acts 6:1-7 as a nomenclature for the seven people elected; it was indeed, "... a title since the apostolic times and it stands for one of the major orders of ministers in the church. The word itself is a Greek word known as *diakonos* (διακονος), and it means servant, attendant, minister. Basically, a deacon is

a servant, an attendant, often a waiter (Jn. 2:5,9). It is sometimes used for an official in the church (Phil. 1:1), or a special gift (Rom. 12:7; service).¹²

The institution of the office is commonly found in the account in Acts 6:1-7. Luke the author of the Acts of the Apostles used the verb word *diakonein* (διακονειν) to describe their function of “serving tables.”¹³ *Webster’s Twentieth Century Dictionary Unabridged* sees deacon as a clergyman ranking just below a priest in Roman Catholic and Anglican Churches. Also in certain other Christian churches, the deacon is a layman appointed to help the minister especially in secular matters, etc.¹⁴ The three major qualifications stated by the apostles in selecting the deacons are: Firstly, they must be known. This qualification is very ethically composite in meaning. This means they must not be strangers or new converts. They must have been among the believers for a long period of time (or years). Such ones must have a good reputation. This characteristic has expression in relation to society, in relation to themselves, and in relation to their homes.¹⁵ “Those holding such a sensitive position would need to be trusted”¹⁶. Therefore, they must not be men of loose reputation but men whose reputation can command respect even outside the church (1 Tim. 3:7). Their reputations have great deal of effects in their stewardship¹⁷. Kisau notes that “many church leaders have failed the test of been above reproach when given the opportunity to manage church resources, especially money”¹⁸. The apostles did not take this principle with hands of levity.

Secondly, they must be filled with the Holy Spirit. The Holy Spirit empowers for service and helps in pleasing the Lord (Heb. 11:6) as well as proving that we are among His people (Rom. 8:14). Kisau opines that “even an administrative task was a spiritual one, and the filling of the Holy Spirit was as much needed for the distribution of food as it was for the preaching of the word. The unity of the community, which these men had to maintain, was as much a witness to the Lord as was the teaching in the name of Jesus.”¹⁹ The role of the Holy Spirit cannot be over emphasized. The Holy Spirit teaches, instructs, guides, reveals things, illuminates, impacts gifts for service, etc.²⁰ So, it becomes a necessary qualification for such ones to be filled with the Holy Spirit. Solomon Adria notes that “it is because deacons also take part in teaching and are not solely responsible for social work in the church that they need to have a secure grasp of the deep truths of the faith (3:9). These deep truths can only be understood by God’s children who are enlightened by the Holy Spirit.”²¹

Thirdly, to be effective in their task, the persons to be elected needed wisdom to distinguish genuine need from wants. *Oxford Dictionary of English* defines wisdom as “the ability to make sensible decisions and give good advice because of the experience and knowledge that you have.”²² Wisdom is the ability to apply knowledge positively to achieve good results. Wisdom is very important in every aspect of human life including our relationship with people. It therefore requires wisdom to apply principle of distribution so that “no one lacked anything, but this also meant that no received more than others... The assistants had to be able to judge the exact amount each person needed.”²³ So these qualifications are pre-requisite to service in the church. As shown “in the practice of the community, wisdom is especially required because dealing with persons plays an important role. It was due to lack of wisdom that the widows of the Greeks were left by the wayside in the distribution activities.”²⁴ Fatokun observes that “...as subordinates to both (bishops and elders) the chief duty of deacons was to assist in Church service and in administering the property of the churches. In addition to those, they visited the sick, the widows and the church at large and brought report to the presbyters or bishop. Owing to its importance, the character qualifications of their office is set side by side with bishop in 1 Tim.3:1-13²⁵.

The Conduct of the Election

Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English opines that election is “when people vote to choose someone for an official position.”²⁶ But Wikipedia sees it as “a formal group decision-making process by which a population chooses an individual or multiple individuals to hold public office.”²⁷ From religious perspective, election is seen by Packer as,

...the act of choice whereby God picks an individual or group out of a larger company for a purpose or destiny of his own appointment. The main OT word for this is the verb *bāḥar*, which expresses the

idea of deliberately selecting someone or something after carefully considering the alternatives... The word implies a decided preference for, sometimes positive pleasure in, the object chosen... In LXX and the NT the corresponding verb is *eklegomai* which implies “choose out for oneself.”²⁸

Unlike the election done in Acts 1:26 where Matthias and Joseph were proposed for the replacement of Judas Iscariot and Matthias was chosen by lots; the actual method or system of election in Acts 6:1-7 was not stated or recorded but it was a method well known and pleased to the congregation. Paul M. Kisau notes that, “it is evidence of the unity of the community that everyone approved of this course of action and was involved in appointing these leaders... There was no factions.”²⁹ Although the total number and names of people scrutinized through the application of the stated qualifications were not mentioned but the names of those who successfully triumphed were stated. The election was free and fair without the interference or influence of the apostles. The conduct was justifiable, peaceful, and equitable, as well as, a plausible, impressive and without protest after election.

Seven men were chosen among who were Stephen, described as a man full of faith and of the Holy Spirit; Philip; Prochorus; Nicanor; Timon; Parmenas; and Nicolas from Antioch, who is described as a convert to Judaism (Acts 6:5). It is of note that all these men have Greek names which inferably connotes that “the community chose people who would be close to those they were serving. The Judean believers were prepared to let other believers control the distribution of goods to everyone.”³⁰ These seven elected men were presented to the apostles for approval and commissioning which the apostles did by praying and laying of hands on them (Acts 6:6). This action serves as the first recorded incident where the laying of hands signifies the approval and commissioning of God’s servants. It therefore became a tradition and it was used also by the leaders at the church of Antioch (Acts 13:3). And Paul in admonishing Timothy in 1 Timothy 5:22 told him not to lay hands on anyone without been subjected to adequate scrutiny.

Implications for National Integration

Nigeria as a nation got her independent from the British rule (United Kingdom) in 1960. At that time her population was estimated and recorded as 45.14 million people and grew to 213.40 million people in 2021. According to *WorldData.Info*, “this is a growth of 372.8 percent in 61 years.”³¹ However, the growth is not static just as been experienced in the early church. It is on increase daily as children are born and immigrants are trooping into the country. According to Wikipedia, “the modern state originated with British colonialization in the 19th century taking its present territorial shape with the merging of the Southern Nigeria Protectorate and Northern Nigeria Protectorate in 1914 by Lord Lugard.”³² Administrative and legal systems were set up by the

British while practicing indirect rule. Isaac notes that “though the system recognized the existence of Emirs, Chiefs and Obis, but the colonial master’s interest and influence were brought to bear on the natives indirectly by the Europeans officer, who dictated the necessary processes that must be obeyed.”³³ European military powers were used to suppress resistance and to enforced compliance to the law that looks like that of the traditional chieftdom hence it was “divide and rule” in disguised.³⁴ However, after the attainment of independence with minimum internal cohesion the country continued as one but an adequate policy which could maintain or absolve the enormous diversities of tribes, languages, culture, as well as, the existing religions in the country was not put in place by the colonial masters. In attempt to bringing a viable unification, the colonialists hopefully formulated a federal constitution in order to bring the diversities under one administrative umbrella but never worked. This was because the nationalists’ activities during the struggle for independence did not only promote religious differences but also political tussle and ethnic rivalry among the people in the country. This had bathed various kinds of predicaments which effects still linger on the nation. Different types of administration had been practiced in the nation ranging from democracy to military rule, and back to democracy from the time of independence.

This indicates that the nation is battling with leadership problem. Due to this, various party systems have been experimented ranging from two- party system to multi-party system.³⁵ The problem still persists in spite of these systems. Leadership problem surfaces continually. This had led to a lot of clamoring and agitating

for division due the systemic corruption and injustice. Ethnic unities are threatened among various nationalities. For instance, some ethnic groups such as Igbo are agitating for Biafra³⁶ and some Yoruba are demanding for an Oduduwa nation. Various reasons gave rise to this demand some of which include nepotism, ethnicism, favoritism, marginalization, inequity, injustice, emergence of irresponsible and selfish leaders at local, state and federal levels who came to power due to questionable polls results.³⁷ This gives room for negligence and infringes on human rights which eventually led to, “the high level of crime, corruption and bribery, wanton destruction of lives and properties worth millions of naira, sectionalism, murder and assassinations, gruesome scene of ethnic groups gleefully slaughtering one another, economic degradation, social vices... the average citizen of the country has to grapple with.”³⁸

The Nigerian masses in demanding for their rights often expressed it through protests, unrest and strikes because it seems to be the only language Nigeria government understands. Consequently, such actions threaten of unity of the nation and also reflect bad leadership. Unlike the early church when such signal was given through grumbling, the apostles (church leaders) did not allow the situation to lead to protests and strikes in any form but they quickly proffered solution to rectify the cause without delay. Nigeria government most often allows such to results in escalatory violence, problem and untold hardship before proffering solution (s) as the signs appear. This has a lot of implication which usually results to chaos, unrest, etc., which signs division.³⁹

As seen in the Early Church, the apostles saddled the disciples with the responsibility of electing seven people to who the “table service” (social work) will be handed over to. Having stated the qualifications for the selection of the candidates, the apostles did not interfere with the operation of the system or the voting decision nor play a political godfather’s roles in influencing the outcomes of the election to their (apostles’ taste) will. Inversely in Nigeria, electoral officers are influenced, bought off as well as some voters by politicians and influential people or leaders. Political leaders or people in power a times give affirmative statement and assuring words of victory in favour of a preferred candidate or aspirant prior to voting or electoral decision. For instance, it is reported on *Punch* Newspaper on 6th February 2022 that “the President, Major General Muhammadu Buhari (retd.), on Monday in Katsina, said the All Progressives Congress will mobilize all of it electoral machinery to ensure the victory of its flag bearer, at the February 25 presidential election... We will work for his victory at the poll.”⁴⁰ This he said during a courtesy call at the Emir’s palace in Katsina. He also mandated the Emir to do same in his domain.

The Presidential election was conducted on 25th February and Tinubu eventually emerged and was declared the winner by INEC. However, this was challenged by Peter Obi of the Labour Party (LP) and Atiku of Peoples Democratic Party (PDP) in the court. This action affected the gubernatorial election which was supposed to hold on 11th March 2023. Consequently, the election was postponed to 18th March 2023. This had implications on many things such as education sector as the resumption of students on 15th March 2023 was also postponed to 20th March 2023. In political sector, there was rancor. Political aspirants had to continue underground work and campaign. In economy sector, people had to leave their work on that day as against their schedule plans, and sacrificed the day to cast their votes. Socially, some people’s expectation in regards to the political scenario in the country was cut short, “letting down” and to cast the next vote will require a lot of efforts and mobilization by the politicians. It is of note that there had been good social relationship among the southerners, easterners, westerners and northerners but this could be marred through unfavourable political actions which could lead to disunity and discord. Its implications will be “the hatred of one tribe, ethnic group or geo- political zone against another.”⁴¹

Leaders with discernment are needed in the nation just as in the Early Church. This will have a great boost on the economic life of the people. In Nigeria today, masses cannot afford to eat balance diet nor eating three square meals. Poverty has become part of and parcel of the daily existence of the masses. Prosperity encircles and recycles among the upper-class citizens. The lower poor’s take-home pay cannot even take them through the month before they receive their next salaries. Workers’ salaries are not even paid in some sectors. This had often led to incessant strike actions with grieving effects on the economy. Thus, economic hardship could trigger

agitation for division or session. The apostles in lessening the hardship of the members distributed food to them (widows), and promptly acted to curb things that could cause division among the people in the church. The unequal distribution of the economic wealth of Nigeria has always been one of the bases for agitation for division. It therefore calls for discerning leaders to elect people to be delegated with power to oversee such sector(s). Such ones should only possess educational qualifications but spiritual as well. The implication of this is to ensure they have the fear of God in their mind, full of God's Spirit and love for humanity. Along with this is having good name among the people which indirectly has links with religion.

Unfortunately, in Nigeria, most people elected into position of power are "letting down" Nigerians thus making one wonder whether they really attend Churches or Mosques. Jegede notes that such ones bear religious names, give offering, dance in churches, pray in Mosques and pay *zakat* but they are not guided by their conscience in their actions because selfishness and disobedience have taken upper hand in their hearts.⁴² But with the presence of many religions in Nigerian society "we expect the nation to be a better place; peaceful and free of moral evil, but contrarily, corruption has become the order of the day. This has become the bedrock of the prevalent vices in Nigeria. The religion which a leader professes, should affect his/her character and attitude..."⁴³The salient issue is imbedded in what was actually left out in electing people into leadership position in Nigeria. Religion is often undermined in Nigerian politic. God is put aside in Nigerian politicking.

Candidates' knowability of God, having His fear, having faith in God, etc. are not taking into consideration before approving candidature and voting for such candidates. The apostles did not overlook this aspect rather they emphasized the divine attributes and virtues which the people to be elected must possess because the stewardship of the candidates will not only be to human but also to God, the owner of the Church. In like manner the services or stewardship of political candidates are not only toward human (who voted and elected them) but also to God who owns every human being and the nation as a whole.

Recommendations

Government should promptly attend to peoples' agitations or complaints before such escalate into chaos. Electoral agency, INEC/ agents should work in the fear of God knowing that they are accountable to both men (Nigeria as a nation) and God, the Creator of all beings and the nation(s). They should be credible in their acts. Scrutiny of candidates to be voted for or elected should be done without favoritism, sentiment and partiality. Such candidates should be proven on good name which encompasses both internal and external relationship with people. The conduct of election and its results should not be played upon by political god fathers and leaders in government to suite their favorites. They should let votes count so as to let the masses trust the government and have confidence in both the incumbent and incoming government. There should be absolute transparency right from the polling centers to collation centers without sentiments.

Leadership qualities should not only be based on academic qualifications but also spiritual too. God works with someone that He can leads, instructs and directs than someone whose heart is far away from God and hardhearted. Apostles' method of electing leaders into service should be integrated in Nigeria by allowing the people (Nigerians) to choose or elect leaders by themselves and such leaders should be approved by the authority just as the apostles did. This will in no small way enhances unity, social, economic and political growth in the nation. It will also lead to peaceful co-existence among the multi-ethnicity and pluralistic religious society of Nigeria. Investment survives and flourishes in a society where there's peace, unity, Security, love and good leadership, which directly or indirectly also attracts investors from other countries as well as citizens in Diasporas. Therefore, if the Nigerian government or leaders could integrate the apostles' approach to solving problem(s) it will go a long way in salvaging the nation from crushing or hitting the rock.

Conclusion

The church's birth has its predictive footing in the Old Testament which came to pass in the New Testament as explained in this paper. Various terms or descriptions are used in defining the term church, such as,

flock/sheep of God, temple, *kyriakon*, *doma*, *ekklesia*, “Bride of Christ,” etc. after the ascension of Jesus Christ and the coming down of the Holy Spirit upon the disciples, there were tremendous growth in the church in Jerusalem. The increase in membership, which was nearly on daily basis, made it more difficult to distribute goods or food effectively to the people. This led to neglect of some widows in having their shares thus, emanating grumbling and complaints which could cause division in the church. The apostles quickly salvaged the situation when the matter was brought to their (apostles) hearing or notice. They saddled the people with the responsibility of electing seven people to who the “table service” will be handed over to. The qualifications were stated and the election was conducted without interference. It was free and fair and well accepted by the people and approved by the apostles. The seven people were commissioned and services or stewardship brought tremendous growth and increase to the church. This paper recommends the integration of similar approach in Nigeria.

Endnotes

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